

1 **Structural Fire Resistance of Partially Restrained, Partially Composite Floor** 2 **Beams, II: Modeling**

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11

12 **Abstract**

13 This paper is Part 2 of a two-part investigation of the structural fire resistance of a partially
14 composite, one-way spanning steel floor beam assembly with partial translational and rotational
15 end restraint provided by shear tab connections to a supporting frame. A preceding paper (Part 1)
16 described a pair of experimental tests on structurally identical composite floor specimens (one
17 protected and the other unprotected) that are subjected to fire via a large modular furnace. In this
18 paper, those experimental results are used to validate numerical models that conservatively capture
19 the thermo-mechanical response of the specimen assemblies to fire. Models are developed to
20 maximize simplicity toward implementing performance-based design of these assemblies in
21 practice. Thermal analysis of the steel is performed using a multiple lumped mass approach, which
22 can be implemented via spreadsheet or a simple, non-iterative programmed solution. Thermal
23 analysis of the slab via a simple one-dimensional heat flow model is compared against a more
24 detailed computational solution. Two types of structural finite element analyses were performed:
25 one composed of shell elements (more complex) and another composed of fiber-beam elements
26 (simpler). The results of all models show conservative agreement with the experimental data.
27 These models are used to analyze the tested assemblies for variations in applied load and fire
28 protection thickness to demonstrate the utility of the ASTM E119 standard fire test as a validation
29 baseline for performance-based structural fire engineering evaluation.

30

31 **Keywords: fire resistance; composite steel beam; passive fire protection; performance-based**
32 **design**

33

34 **1. Introduction**

35 In current practice, the design of fire protection for steel-framed buildings is typically
36 performed using so-called “prescriptive” requirements, by which active and passive fire protection
37 measures are selected according to provisions in the building code [1]. Active fire protection
38 primarily consists of sprinklers and other fire suppression systems, and passive fire protection
39 typically consists of encasement or coating materials that are applied to the structural elements.
40 For the majority of composite floor systems in the US, passive fire protection consists of spray-
41 applied fire resistive material (SFRM) which is field applied to the floor beams as an
42 approximately contoured layer. Based on the building’s size, occupancy, and function, the 2018
43 International Building Code (IBC) [1] requires that an hourly rating of passive fire protection be
44 applied to the structural elements based on the results of experimental tests referred to as
45 “standard” fire tests, such as ASTM E119 [2] and ISO 834 [3]. Hourly ratings for composite floor
46 assemblies, such as those documented in the UL product specification catalog [4], can be
47 determined via limits on the temperature increase in the steel elements and/or the rate/magnitude
48 of load-induced deflection. Nearly all composite floor assemblies in steel buildings (most
49 consisting of wide-flange steel beams supporting a composite reinforced concrete floor slab) will
50 not exactly match those evaluated via the standard fire test. Conversion equations for translating
51 SFRM requirements from the tested assemblies to an actual structure are provided in references
52 such as ASCE 29-05 [5] and AISC Design Guide 19 [6]. Specifically, the SFRM thickness needed

53 to achieve a prescribed hourly rating for a particular beam section is calculated by comparing its
54 ratio of cross-sectional area to fire-exposed perimeter (W/D) against that of the tested section.

55 For many conventional steel building designs, the prescriptive methods may provide an
56 efficient and relatively cost effective approach to providing minimum levels of passive fire
57 resistance. However, there are ambiguities in the translation of hourly ratings from standard fire
58 tested specimens to actual composite floor systems. Previous research has shown that the
59 structural performance of fire-exposed composite beams with SFRM thicknesses obtained via the
60 ASCE 29-05 conversion can vary based on the load level, span length, steel section size, slab
61 dimensions, boundary conditions, and fire exposure intensity [7]. In some cases, composite beams
62 with little to no passive fire protection can also demonstrate fire resistance when subjected to
63 realistic fires that include a decay phase to burnout [8,9].

64 In North American practice, prescriptive fire protection requirements for floor systems in
65 steel buildings are predicated on a classification of being either unrestrained or restrained to
66 thermal expansion. Both ASTM E119 [2] and the 2018 IBC [1] stipulate that engineering
67 judgment must be exercised to determine whether the surrounding or supporting structure is
68 sufficient to restrain thermal expansion – there is currently no standardized method for establishing
69 a sufficient level of restraint in the actual structure to correlate to standard fire test results. Both
70 experimental [8,10,11] and numerical studies [9,12,13] have generally supported the expectation
71 that at least some restraint of thermally induced expansion and deflection in composite floor
72 systems under fire will enhance their resistance versus an unrestrained subassembly (which
73 represents a conservative lower bound that is not realistically achievable in actual construction).
74 However, some of these studies have also suggested that increased restraint may actually induce a
75 faster onset of plastic behavior in some fire-exposed composite floor beams [12], and optimum

76 fire resistance may be obtained at partial (i.e. less than full) restraint [7,14]. Thermal restraint of
77 steel beam floor systems has been identified as the cause of significant damage in several high-
78 rise fires [7], in which deflections due to yielding and buckling of steel floor members caused
79 losses of compartmentation as well as local failure of connections and the slab.

80 Performance-based structural-fire analysis methods can extend past the current simple
81 conversions for SFRM thickness to examine the changes in demand and capacity that occur as a
82 structural member is heated and account for the influence of span length, boundary conditions,
83 slab properties, and applied loading. Per section 703.4.4 of the 2018 IBC, engineering analysis
84 can be used to demonstrate fire resistance equivalent to the prescriptive requirements [1].
85 Performance-based methods for calculating the behavior of steel structures under fire have been a
86 part of the Eurocode for over a decade [15], and performance-based provisions are now
87 increasingly available in North American practice via Appendix 4 in AISC 360-16 [16], Appendix
88 E in ASCE 7-16 [17], and ASCE's *Manual of Practice 138: Structural Fire Engineering* [18].
89 These references stipulate that an analysis of a steel structure's mechanical response to fire must
90 account for the degradation of material strength and stiffness due to increased temperature as well
91 as the effects of thermal expansion and large deflection.

92 This project contributes to the development of a performance-based framework for fire
93 resistant design of composite steel-beam floor systems with a pair of new large-scale experimental
94 tests and associated numerical modeling. Part 1 of this study [19] presented the results of two
95 large-scale fire tests that were performed on structurally identical composite floor assemblies
96 typical of North American construction practice and partially restrained to thermal expansion. The
97 wide-flange beam of one specimen was protected with an applied thickness of spray-applied fire
98 resistive material (SFRM) corresponding to a 2-hr ASTM E119 fire resistance rating (calculated

99 using the current conversion based on W/D ratios [5,6]), and the other had no passive fire protection
100 (i.e. unprotected). The results showed that the protected composite beam reached nearly 90 min of
101 fire resistance per E119 thermal limit criteria [2]. The protected beam also demonstrated nearly
102 130 min of structural fire resistance per deflection limit criteria with an applied flexural load that
103 represented 60% of a maximum service condition. The unprotected specimen reached almost 30
104 minutes of structural fire resistance before reaching runaway failure at the same load level and
105 demonstrated very similar deflection versus beam temperature as the protected specimen.

106 Using the experimental data from Part 1 as validation, this paper uses thermal and structural
107 analysis methods of varying complexity to capture the flexural response and failure of the fire-
108 exposed composite floor beam specimens. The goal of this modeling effort is to develop accurate,
109 conservative predictions of fire-induced mechanics and limit states at reduced computational cost,
110 thus increasing the accessibility of these methods to practicing engineers. Performance-based
111 models that are validated against standard fire test results can be used as an improved tool for
112 translating fire resistance ratings based on those tests to composite floor systems in realistic steel
113 buildings. In this paper, variations in applied load and SFRM thickness will be examined to
114 evaluate the relationship between structural response and the ASTM E119 thermal limit criteria
115 for tested composite floor beam specimens.

116

117 **2. Background**

118 Several previous studies have used data from fire tests of composite steel floor beams that
119 are supported with shear connections to successfully validate a variety of numerical modeling
120 approaches. These studies have used a combination of shell and solid finite elements [20,21] for
121 an in-depth examination of not only the beam but also the shear connection when a one-way

122 spanning composite assembly is subjected to heat-induced weakening and restraint of thermal
123 expansion. These efforts have contributed valuable understanding of the damage sustained by the
124 composite floor; however, they have significant computational cost and may not be conducive to
125 design practice. Also, these studies focused primarily on the response of unprotected assemblies
126 with a variety of thermal exposures, not necessarily on assemblies with applied passive fire
127 protection. To meet the need for design-basis tools, analytical fiber-based predictions of composite
128 floor behavior have been developed [22,23] and validated against experimental tests that
129 demonstrated plastic flexural behavior. Those tests exhibited little local or global instability due
130 to either the size of the specimen or the degree of restraint. This study will build on these previous
131 contributions to also consider potential instability and provide a direct validation for both a
132 protected and unprotected specimen in the context of the standard fire test. For practical
133 implementation, simple yet conservative models are advantageous, and this study therefore aims
134 at validating models that would be increasingly accessible to structural engineering practitioners.

135 Several studies have expanded past the one-way spanning assumption to model composite
136 floor systems as part of a 3D system for the purposes of model validation [24,25] or parametric
137 study of prototype composite floor systems with regular [26] or irregular [9] framing layouts.
138 These studies typically utilize shell elements for the slab and fiber-beam elements for the steel
139 beams in order to maximize computational efficiency and demonstrate the contribution of the
140 slab's two-way action to the fire resistance of the assembly. The objective in most of these studies
141 has been to demonstrate potential enhancements in fire resistance offered by the membrane
142 response of the slab, to the point that passive fire protection could be reduced or eliminated from
143 the secondary floor beams. As a result, the mechanics of the slab's membrane contribution have
144 been examined in-depth [27,28], and several simplified calculation approaches to account for the

145 slab's two-way contribution have been proposed [13,29]. Full-scale fire tests of steel-framed
146 buildings at Cardington [8,30] have demonstrated the ability of two-way slab action to enhance
147 the resistance of unprotected composite floor beams to realistic fire scenarios that include a decay
148 phase to burnout. Though the two-way slab response offers the potential for increased structural
149 efficiency and value engineering to reduce passive fire protection, both experimental [31] and
150 numerical [32] studies have noted limitations of the two-way slab contribution as well as
151 accompanying needs for future research. These include the need for significant stiffness in the
152 framing supporting the secondary beams (the supporting framing is also heated in most fire
153 scenarios), the need for square or nearly square aspect ratios of composite floor bays, slab detailing
154 to resist increased membrane stresses at larger deflection, and connection detailing at the ends of
155 the secondary beams to withstand large reaction forces and rotations. As the research of two-way
156 slab contributions to composite floor systems continues to advance, the evaluation of composite
157 floor systems as one-way spanning elements remains an appropriately conservative approach [33]
158 for integrating performance-based structural-fire analysis into the current design environment for
159 composite floors in steel buildings.

160 A key aspect of modeling composite floor assemblies is the appropriate representation of
161 the beam-to-slab interface, achieved using cast-in headed shear studs. Wang et al. [23] provided
162 numerical validation of a pair of experimental tests on composite beams with a flat slab [34] that
163 differed only in their composite percentage. The models included temperature dependent material
164 properties and consideration of the shear-slip behavior of the shear connectors. Modeling results
165 showed good agreement with test data and confirmed that the 50% composite specimen exhibited
166 a similar fire-induced failure time as the fully composite specimen. Essentially, the specimens
167 became increasingly composite since the steel beam experienced a more rapid rise in temperature

168 than the slab or shear studs. Fischer and Varma [21] also showed that assuming full composite
169 action led to conservative midspan deflection predictions under several fire scenarios. Modeling
170 by Mirza and Uy [35] indicated that composite beams with solid flat slab configurations experience
171 increased shear demand and deformation in the stud connectors, whereas composite beams with
172 profiled slabs on fluted decks are able to develop the full compressive capacity of the concrete and
173 demonstrate greater structural resistance to fire loading. Further testing on short-span specimens
174 with low composite action [31] and long-span specimens with higher composite action [36] also
175 showed no noticeable shear stud damage. Collectively, these previous studies suggest that design-
176 basis models of composite assemblies with fluted decks (which is typical North American practice)
177 can appropriately capture their fire-induced response by utilizing a simplified “very stiff”
178 assumption of the shear interface between the slab and beam. The validity of this assumption will
179 be demonstrated in the analyses presented in this paper.

180

181 **3. Tested Specimens**

182 As was discussed in Part 1 of this study [19], two one-way spanning composite beam
183 specimens were loaded to utilize 35% of their ambient factored nominal moment capacity and
184 subjected to the ASTM E119 standard fire curve [2] using a modular structural testing furnace
185 until the onset of flexural runaway failure. Full details of the specimen design, experimental setup,
186 and test results are provided in the Part 1 companion paper, but a brief summary is provided here.
187 The two structurally identical composite floor beam specimens were constructed using a W12 × 26
188 hot-rolled steel beam (7850 kg/m³ [490 pcf]) with a yield strength of 345 MPa (50 ksi) at a span
189 of 3.34-m (10-ft. 11½-in.). The beam supports a 142-cm (56-in.) wide lightweight concrete (LWC)
190 slab with tested density of 1938 kg/m³ (121 pcf) and an 82.6-mm (3.25-in.) thickness on top of a

191 50.8-mm (2-in.) fluted metal deck. The slab was designed with 27.6 MPa (4 ksi) nominal
192 compressive strength (cylinders broken on each test day showed only ~5% increase beyond
193 nominal) and was reinforced with 6x6 4GA welded wire reinforcement (WWR) placed 19.05-mm
194 (3/4-in.) below the top face of the slab. The composite beam is designed to be partially composite
195 using ten 19.05-mm (3/4-in.) diameter, 101.6-mm (4-in.) long shear studs that are spaced at 304.8-
196 mm (1-ft.) intervals within each flute (in the weak position) in the deck. Based on AISC
197 specifications [16], the specimens were calculated to be 23.6% composite at ambient temperature
198 based on the nominal properties of the concrete slab, steel beam, and the shear studs (these
199 calculations are provided in [37]). The beam was perpendicularly connected to the web of a
200 C15×40 channel (which provided transverse gravity support to the slab) at each end via a shear
201 tab connection with three 19.05-mm (3/4-in.) ASTM A325 bolts with nominal shear strengths of
202 372 MPa (54 ksi) [16]. The outside face of each channel web was bolted to the interior flange face
203 of a W10×26 column, which provided vertical support and partial flexural restraint of thermal
204 expansion. The columns were connected to a heavy self-reacting frame by clevis pin connections
205 at the top and bottom, with the top clevis permitted to slide vertically to avoid unnecessary axial
206 force buildup in the columns due to thermal expansion.

207 One specimen was left unprotected (i.e. with no passive fire protection), and the other was
208 protected with SFRM in accordance with 2014 UL Design No. D902 [38], which is commonly
209 used in current steel building practice. An average thickness of 22.2-mm (7/8-in.) of CAFCO 300
210 [39] was applied to achieve a 2-hr fire resistance rating for both a restrained assembly and
211 unrestrained beam. No SFRM was applied to the underside of the fluted deck in accordance with
212 the D902 design. Several layers of ceramic wool blankets were used to wrap the transverse
213 channels and the W10×26 support columns to mitigate their temperature increase during the fire

214 tests. The average steel temperature in the columns reached $\sim 600^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $\sim 250^{\circ}\text{C}$ in the protected
215 and unprotected tests, respectively, due to the 100-min difference in test duration [19]. A single
216 wrap of ceramic wool blankets was also applied to the shear tab connection zone and extended
217 roughly 355-mm (14-in.) from the end of the beam. In accordance with the 2018 International
218 Building Code [1], the end connections of a secondary composite floor beam would receive the
219 same hourly rating of passive fire protection as the supporting girder, even though the rating for
220 the beam is often lower than that of the girder. Applying a single wrap of ceramic wool blanket to
221 the connection zone simulates this requirement while still allowing some increase in the connection
222 temperature as if it were sprayed with SFRM (which was applied before the specimen was installed
223 into the test fixture).

224 The specimens were loaded in four-point bending at their third-points using a long-stroke
225 single-acting hydraulic cylinder that was inversely mounted to the large header beam of the self-
226 reacting frame. The cylinder exerted a constant load of 158 kN (35.5 kips) onto a steel-framed
227 loading tree, which evenly split the load into two load points. In combination with the specimen
228 self-weight (3.27 kN/m [224 plf]), the applied load utilized 35% of the composite section's
229 factored nominal moment capacity (calculated as $\phi M_n = 266.1 \text{ kN}\cdot\text{m}$ [196.3 kip-ft], where $\phi=0.9$
230 [16,40]).

231

232 4. Thermal Analysis

233 Thermal analyses of the beam and slab in the composite specimens are performed using
234 separate uncoupled calculation approaches, the details of which are described below.

235

236 4.1 Beam Temperatures

237 Simplified heat transfer for the composite steel beam is performed using a three lumped
 238 mass approach that is adapted from previously published approaches for unprotected floor beams
 239 [41] and non-uniformly heated beam-columns with and without fire protection [42]. All lumped
 240 mass calculations in this study were implemented using MATLAB [43] but are also conducive to
 241 implementation in a spreadsheet. As shown in **Fig. 1**, the flanges and web are each represented as
 242 a lumped mass (assumed to have a uniform temperature) located at their respective centers of
 243 gravity. **Fig. 1** shows the heat transfer from the fire to each lumped mass at its exposed surfaces
 244 (Q_{in}) as well as conduction from the top flange to the slab ($Q_{tf \rightarrow slab}$) and between lumped masses
 245 (for example $Q_{bf \rightarrow w}$). The application of energy conservation yields the following equations that
 246 can be used to calculate the change in temperature from time step $i-1$ to i ($T_{s,j,i} = T_{s,j,i-1} + \Delta T_{s,j,i}$) for
 247 each lumped mass j in the floor beam cross-section:

$$248 \quad \Delta T_{s,bf,i} = \left(\frac{Q_{in,bf,i} - Q_{bf \rightarrow w,i}}{\rho_s c_{s,bf,i-1} A_{s,bf} + (\rho_p c_{p,bf,i-1} d_p P_{p,bf}) / 2} \right) \Delta t \quad (1a)$$

$$249 \quad \Delta T_{s,w,i} = \left(\frac{Q_{in,w,i} + Q_{bf \rightarrow w,i} - Q_{w \rightarrow tf,i}}{\rho_s c_{s,w,i-1} A_{s,w} + (\rho_p c_{p,w,i-1} d_p P_{p,w}) / 2} \right) \Delta t \quad (1b)$$

$$250 \quad \Delta T_{s,tf,i} = \left(\frac{Q_{in,tf,i} + Q_{w \rightarrow tf,i} - Q_{tf \rightarrow slab,i}}{\rho_s c_{s,tf,i-1} A_{s,tf} + (\rho_p c_{p,tf,i-1} d_p P_{p,tf}) / 2} \right) \Delta t \quad (1c)$$

251 where ρ_s and c_s are the density (kg/m³) and specific heat (J/kg-K) of steel; ρ_p , c_p , and d_p are the
 252 density, specific heat, and thickness (m) of the SFRM; A_s is the cross-sectional area of the steel
 253 lumped mass fiber (m²); P_p is the fire exposed perimeter (m) of the SFRM; and Δt is the time step
 254 (sec). The first term in the Eq. 1 denominators represents the heat energy absorbed by steel in each
 255 lumped mass during the time step. The second term represents the heat energy absorbed by the

256 SFRM applied to the lumped mass – if no fire protection is applied, this term reduces to zero.
 257 Thermal conduction along the length of the beam can also be considered per previous work by
 258 Quiel et al [44]; however, this study assumes uniform fire exposure along the length of the beam
 259 when calculating its temperature increase.

260
 261 **Fig. 1.** Three lumped mass heat transfer model for a composite steel floor beam.
 262 Different formulations for Q_{in} are used for surfaces that are either unprotected or protected
 263 with a layer of SFRM with thickness d_p :

264 *Unprotected:*
$$Q_{in,j,i} = P_{u,j} \left[h(T_{f,i} - T_{s,j,(i-1)}) + \sigma \varepsilon \left((T_{f,i} + 273)^4 - (T_{s,j,(i-1)} + 273)^4 \right) \right] \quad (2)$$

265 *Protected:*
$$Q_{in,j,i} = \frac{P_{p,j} k_{p,j,i-1} (T_{f,i} - T_{s,j,(i-1)})}{d_p} \quad (3)$$

266 where j is the lumped mass fiber; i denotes the time step; $T_{f,i}$ is the fire temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$); and $T_{s,j,(i-1)}$ is the temperature of the steel ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) at the previous time step, $i-1$. $T_{f,i}$ is set equal to the fire
267 temperature halfway through the current time step i (i.e. at time $t_{i-1} + \Delta t/2$) to approximate the
268 average fire exposure during that time step [45]. Heat transfer to the unprotected steel surfaces
269 includes both convective and radiative heat transfer. In Eq. 2, P_u is the perimeter (m) of the
270 unprotected steel surface; h is the heated convective heat transfer coefficient (equal to $25 \text{ W/m}^2\text{-K}$
271 per Eurocode 1 for exposure to standard fires [46]); ε is the resultant emissivity from the emitting
272 and receiving surfaces (taken equal to 0.5 [47]); and σ is the Stefan-Boltzmann constant ($56.7\text{E-}9$
273 $\text{W/m}^2\text{-K}^4$). The fire-exposed perimeter for the bottom flange and web includes all surfaces
274 assuming full exposure to a compartment fire. The fire-exposed perimeter for the top flange will
275 be reduced by its contact with the slab. For this configuration of slab on fluted deck, P_u for the top
276 flange is calculated by assuming that half of the top face of the top flange will be in contact with
277 the slab and therefore unexposed and the other half will still be exposed to fire (i.e. $P_{u,tf} = P_{u,bf} - b_f$
278 $/2$). The ratio of shielded to exposed surface for the top face of the top flange could be adjusted
279 depending on the profile of the deck in other composite floor designs.
280

281 In Eq. 3, P_p is the perimeter (m) of the outer contoured surface of the fire protection, and
282 k_p is the thermal conductivity (W/m-K) of the fire protection material. P_p accounts for the
283 insulation thickness and is calculated assuming no heat transfer from the fire to the top face of the
284 top flange (i.e. the gaps between the fluted deck and the top flange will be filled with SFRM). Heat
285 transfer calculations for protected surfaces assume that the external surface of the insulation has
286 the same temperature as the fire and the internal surface has the same temperature as the steel
287 [15,45]. The gradient between these temperatures through the thickness of the SFRM is
288 conservatively assumed to be linear. The energy absorption terms for the protection in Eqs. 1a and

289 1b also reflect this linear gradient assumption via a factor of 2 in the denominator (i.e. the
 290 temperature of the fire protection approximately represents the average of the fire and steel
 291 temperatures). Note that Eurocode 3 replaces the 2 in the denominator of this term with 3 and
 292 includes an additional adjustment factor to reduce the conservatism of the linear thermal gradient
 293 assumption [15]. Eq. 1 could be modified to incorporate the Eurocode adjustments if needed to
 294 improve agreement with test results for other fire protection types or thicknesses.

295 All thermal properties of hot-rolled steel and SFRM insulation are modeled as temperature
 296 dependent per Eurocode 3 [15] and published data for materials similar to CAFCO 300 [48]. **Table**
 297 **1** summarizes the temperature dependent thermal properties of the SFRM, which is assumed to
 298 have a constant density of 240 kg/m^3 (15 pcf) (i.e. only the specific heat is considered as the
 299 temperature dependent variable although both will realistically change during a fire [49]). To avoid
 300 iterating to convergence within each time step, temperature-dependent thermal properties for steel
 301 at the current time step are calculated for each lumped mass according to its steel temperature at
 302 the previous time step $i-1$ ($T_{s,j,i-1}$). To calculate updated material properties for the fire protection,
 303 its temperature is approximated using the aforementioned linear thermal gradient assumption as
 304 the average of T_f at the current time step (again, calculated for time $t_{i-1} + \Delta t/2$) and $T_{s,j,i-1}$. This
 305 “one-step lag” strategy can be used to obtain acceptably accurate predictions of steel temperature
 306 increase via lumped mass analysis as long as the time step remains sufficiently short [42]. In this
 307 study, a conservatively small time step of 5 sec is used for all thermal calculations.

308 **Table 1.** Temperature-dependent SFRM thermal properties [48,50]

Temperature °C (°F)	Thermal Conductivity W/m-K (BTU/hr-ft-°F)	Specific Heat J/kg-K (BTU/lbm-°F)
20 (68)	0.059 (0.034)	862 (0.21)
204 (400)	0.076 (0.044)	1008 (0.24)
399 (750)	0.120 (0.069)	1272 (0.30)

1093 (2000)

0.290 (0.170)

1464 (0.35)

309

310 Depending on the dimensions of the beam, Q_{in} per Eq. 2 could be reduced via the Eurocode
 311 3 shadow effect correction factor [15]; however, this factor was not included for the unprotected
 312 W12x26 specimen in this study for simplicity. If the steel beam has any surfaces that are not
 313 exposed to fire but are instead exposed to ambient temperature, Eqs. 2 and 3 can be reformulated
 314 to obtain Q_{out} from each lumped mass using the temperature difference between the steel and the
 315 ambient environment. For this study, however, all surfaces on the beam are assumed to be exposed
 316 to the furnace's internal temperature.

317 Heat transfer between lumped masses j and k ($Q_{j \rightarrow k}$) also assumes that the linkage between
 318 them has a linear thermal gradient:

$$319 \quad Q_{j \rightarrow k} = \frac{t_w (T_{s,j,i-1} - T_{s,k,i-1})}{d_{j \rightarrow k}} \left(\frac{k_{s,j,i-1} + k_{s,k,i-1}}{2} \right) \quad (4)$$

320 where $d_{j \rightarrow k}$ is the distance between the centers of gravity of the lumped masses, t_w is the thickness
 321 of the web (which serves as the effective thermal pathway between the plates), and k_s is the thermal
 322 conductivity (W/m-K) of the steel. The thermal conductivity between lumped masses is
 323 approximated as the average of their temperature dependent values (again calculated using results
 324 from the previous time step).

325 A simplified calculation for heat transfer from the top flange to the slab via their contact
 326 surfaces, $Q_{tf \rightarrow slab}$, is adapted from Ghojel and Wong [41], who developed a polynomial regression
 327 based on a suite of finite element analyses for typical wide-flange composite floor beams subjected
 328 to a standard fire curve. The regression equation for heat flux, $q_{tf \rightarrow slab}$ (W/m²), from the beam's top
 329 flange to a slab in contact with its top face per **Fig. 1** is formulated as follows:

$$q_{tf \rightarrow slab,i} = a + bT_{s,tf,i-1} + cT_{s,tf,i-1}^2 + dT_{s,tf,i-1}^3 + eT_{s,tf,i-1}^4 + fT_{s,tf,i-1}^5 + \frac{g}{b_f} + \frac{h}{b_f^2} \quad (5)$$

where $a = 7025.058155$, $b = 92.10056821$, $c = -0.325555284$, $d = 0.000809452$, $e = -1.02099E-6$, $f = 4.671E-10$, $g = -2786576.15$, $h = 240879025.7$, and flange width b_f in millimeters [41]. Heat transfer $Q_{tf \rightarrow slab}$ for a slab on fluted deck that is in contact with approximately half of the top face of the top flange can then be calculated as follows:

$$Q_{tf \rightarrow slab,i} = \frac{b_f}{2} \left(\frac{q_{tf \rightarrow slab,i}}{2} \right) \quad (6)$$

Fig. 2 plots a comparison of the lumped mass predictions of steel temperature and the test data, which represent the temperature time histories for the flanges and web that are averaged across the three longitudinal measurement locations at the quarter points [19]. The test data includes the cooling phase once burners were turned off, while the lumped mass predictions continue to increase based on the idealized ASTM E119 fire shown in the plots. Since all tests and simulations are performed to flexural failure, the thermal modeling of this decay phase is outside the scope of this study. To accommodate the cooling phase, the only change to the three lumped mass method would be to decrease the convective heat transfer coefficient at the initiation of cooling from an actively heated value (for this study, $h = 25 \text{ W/m}^2\text{-K}$ for standard fires) to a lower value (ranging from 4 to 9 $\text{W/m}^2\text{-K}$) for surfaces either cooling or not exposed to fire [46]. Three lumped mass modeling with a cooling phase has been previously demonstrated by the authors in the analysis of a similar composite beam test utilized a natural fire (with a decay phase to burnout) [37].

For the protected test (**Fig. 2a**), the lumped mass predictions show conservative agreement with the test data for all three plates. Potential causes of the slight overestimation (particularly for the bottom flange and web) include realistic variation in SFRM thickness versus the specified

352 design value, slight variation of as-tested SFRM thermal properties from published information
 353 [49,50], the assumption of a linear thermal gradient through the SFRM layer, and the assumption
 354 that the outside edge of the fire protection is equal to the furnace temperature. For the unprotected
 355 test (**Fig. 2b**), the lumped mass approach shows **good overall** agreement with the test results. Time
 356 histories of the heat flux from the top flange to the slab per Eq. 5 are plotted in **Fig. 3**. The protected
 357 and unprotected lumped mass calculations develop similar trends and maximum values of $q_{tf \rightarrow slab}$,
 358 just at different rates. Not only does the lumped mass calculation require minimal computing
 359 power compared to finite element solutions, but it can also be more easily tailored to the
 360 characteristics of a particular composite floor beam configuration by accounting for the shadow
 361 effect factor or the incomplete contact between the top flange and a slab on fluted deck.

362
 363 **Fig. 2.** Beam temperature comparison for the (a) protected and (b) unprotected tests

364
 365 **Fig. 3.** Heat flux from the top flange to the slab per Eq. 5
 366

367 *4.2 Slab Temperatures*

368 The composite slab will realistically develop a thermal gradient through its thickness due
369 to the low thermal conductivity of the concrete, and lumped mass methods are therefore not an
370 appropriate simplified tool to predict a slab’s fire-induced temperature increase. Instead, a simple
371 one-dimensional heat transfer analysis is performed for both the minimum 82.55-mm (3.25-in.)
372 and maximum 133.35-mm (5.25-in.) thicknesses of the slab (see **Fig. 4a** and **c**) to obtain the
373 average temperature gradient through its structural (i.e. minimum) thickness. For comparison, a
374 two-dimensional finite element analysis of a section of the slab on fluted deck (**Fig. 4b**) was
375 created using GiD 13.0.3 [51] and thermally analyzed in SAFIR 2016 [52]. Temperature dependent
376 properties for siliceous concrete are taken according to Eurocode 2 [53] and assume the midrange
377 value for thermal conductivity according to that standard. The thin metal deck has little thermal
378 resistance or capacity and was therefore neglected in this analysis.

379 The ASTM E119 standard fire curve is applied to the bottom surface of the slab in all three
380 models, and heated surfaces are assigned a convective coefficient $h_f = 25 \text{ W/m}^2\text{-K}$ and emissivity
381 $\varepsilon = 0.7$ [53]. The unheated top surface of the slab is subjected to ambient conditions of 20°C and
382 experiences both radiative (with $\varepsilon = 0.7$) and convective (with $h_a = 4 \text{ W/m}^2\text{-K}$ [46]) heat loss. The
383 vertical edges shown in **Fig. 4** are modeled as adiabatic, thus assuming continuity. Both simple
384 models were discretized into equal six layers with 13.75-mm (0.55-in.) thickness, and the fluted
385 2D model was auto-meshed into fibers with 13.75-mm (0.55-in.) maximum edge dimension.
386 Preliminary analyses showed that these levels of discretization were adequately small to achieve
387 solution convergence.

388 Two sets of temperature-time histories at each of the equally spaced dashed lines in **Fig. 4**
389 were calculated: an average of the two 1D models, and an average of all nodes across the width of
390 each layer in the realistic 2D model. In **Fig. 5**, the simplified “flat slab” average shows good

391 agreement with the 2D model. At ~80-min into the E119 fire duration, the flat average predictions
 392 become slightly lower. The prediction could potentially be improved by weighting the
 393 temperatures obtained in the minimum thickness 1D model and considering top flange heat
 394 transfer. For the purpose of this study, the average 1D temperatures will be used in all simplified
 395 structural analyses to evaluate their ability to capture the experimental flexural behavior of the
 396 tested specimens. The average thru-thickness temperatures from the more realistic 2D model will
 397 be used in structural models with greater complexity, in order to more precisely represent the tested
 398 performance.

402 **Fig. 4.** Slab temperatures at runaway failure time of the protected test specimen (138 min) for
 403 exposure to the ASTM E119 standard fire: (a) minimum, (b) realistic, and (c) maximum
 404 thicknesses.

408 **Fig. 5.** Comparison of slab model temperatures at the thru-thickness locations marked in **Fig. 4**

408 In **Fig. 6**, the temperature-time histories from the 1D and 2D slab thermal modeling
 409 approaches at the top face of the slab are compared to data from the protected and unprotected
 410 tests. The protected test data shows closest agreement with the 1D model of the 133.35-mm (5.25-

411 in.) maximum slab thickness. During that test, water escaping the heated concrete began to collect
 412 and vaporize at the top slab surface. The thermocouples on the top of slab came into contact with
 413 this water, which can be observed by the test temperature plateau in **Fig. 6a** at 100°C (i.e. water's
 414 boiling point) from the 50- to 100-min mark. Due to the water interference, these experimental
 415 measurements data do not fully describe the heat flow through the slab.

416
 417 **Fig. 6.** Top of slab temperature comparison for the (a) protected and (b) unprotected test

418
 419 **Fig. 6b** shows a similar level of agreement between the models and test data for the
 420 unprotected test as was shown for the first 30 minutes of the protected test. The protected test ran
 421 for a longer period of time, allowing the slab to absorb more heat and thus reach a higher
 422 temperature than the shorter, unprotected test. Temperatures were not measured through the slab
 423 thickness during these experimental tests – thru-thickness measurements of the slab temperature
 424 will be prioritized in experimental tests performed during the next phase of this project.

425
 426 *4.3 Thermal Effects on Composite Percentage*

427 As was shown in previous studies [23], the composite action of these specimens will
 428 increase over the duration of each fire test since the steel beam will experience a larger increase in
 429 average temperature than the slab or the shear studs. The composite percentage at each time step
 430 was recalculated per AISC 360-16 [16] to account for the temperature-induced decrease in material

431 properties in the beam, slab, and shear studs. Further documentation of these calculations is
432 provided in [37]. Since experimental measurements of the thru-thickness slab temperature are not
433 available, the calculated temperatures in the beam and slab are used to make a consistent estimate
434 of the time history of composite percentage. The steel temperature was calculated as a weighted
435 average of the lumped mass results in Fig. 2. The average temperature in the minimum structural
436 thickness of the slab was calculated using the average results of the two simplified 1D models in
437 Fig. 4. The shear stud temperature was approximated as the mean of the average slab temperature
438 and steel top flange temperature, which is consistent with observations reported by Selden [54]
439 from other fire tests on composite floor systems where the stud temperature was monitored. Fig.
440 7 shows that the unprotected assembly reaches full composite action at 25 minutes of exposure to
441 the E119 standard fire, and the protected assembly reaches full composite action at 133 minutes.

442
443 **Fig. 7.** Time histories of the composite percentage in the protected and unprotected test
444 assemblies.
445

446 5. Structural Analysis

447 As shown in Fig. 9, two types of structural models were created in SAFIR 2016 [52] with
448 different levels of complexity. In the “complex” option, the composite beam and slab are
449 composed of 3D shell elements, and the shear tab connection and shear studs are explicitly
450 represented at their tested locations. This model is used to obtain a more precise prediction of the

451 tested specimen behavior, particularly to allow the emergence of potential local or global
 452 instability. In the “simple” option, the composite beam and slab are modeled as a single fiber-beam
 453 cross-section, thereby assuming full composite action between the two. Though the 2D fiber-beam
 454 model cannot explicitly consider stability limit states, the potential for local buckling is checked
 455 at every time step using an effective stress approach proposed by the SAFIR developers [55], and
 456 the potential for lateral torsional buckling is evaluated per Vila Real et al. [56]. Note that **Fig. 9** is
 457 shown with symmetry for brevity – both models are analyzed using the full assembly (i.e. with the
 458 full span and both support columns) to avoid the complication of enforcing symmetric boundary
 459 conditions at midspan (especially for the 3D shell model). Temperature dependent structural
 460 properties for hot-rolled steel, siliceous concrete, and the steel WWR are taken according to
 461 Eurocode [15,53]. **Sample temperature-dependent stress-strain curves for steel and concrete are**
 462 **shown in Fig. 8.** Yield strengths for the steel beam and WWR are assigned nominal values of 345
 463 MPa (50 ksi) and 420 MPa (60 ksi), respectively. Concrete compressive strength is assigned a
 464 nominal value of 27.6 MPa (4 ksi), and tensile concrete strength is conservatively neglected.
 465 **SAFIR’s structural concrete model allows fibers that reach their tensile capacity (or in this study,**
 466 **those that experience any tensile strain) to “crack” and contribute zero stress to the mechanics of**
 467 **the cross-section [57]. Residual stresses are neglected in all models for this study.**

468

469

Fig. 8. Temperature-dependent stress-strain relationships

470 In both models, the support columns were represented as fiber-beam elements with 22 strip
471 fibers over the depth of the cross-section (one in each flange and the rest equally spaced in the
472 web) and 14 element discretizations along their 3.77-m (12'-4¼") length. The modeled length of
473 the column was taken as the centerline distance between the shear pins in each clevis. The top
474 clevis has vertically slotted holes and is therefore modeled as a vertical roller. **Fig. 9** shows that
475 the column length within the furnace is heated while the lengths outside the furnace are
476 approximated as remaining at ambient temperature. Though covered with ceramic fiber blankets
477 during the tests, the column section within the furnace experienced a relatively uniform
478 temperature increase [19]. The average column temperature-time history obtained from the test
479 results (measured at the column mid-height within the furnace) is assigned uniformly to all fibers
480 in the heated column sections to avoid performing thermal analysis for these elements.

481
482

Fig. 9. Structural modeling options: 2D fiber-beam and 3D shell

483 Self-weight is applied as a gravity load to each discretized shell or fiber-beam element per
 484 the material properties in Section 3. Though not explicitly modeled in either the 3D shell or 2D
 485 fiber-beam model, the weight of the perpendicular ribs in the slab is applied as an additional
 486 smeared load to the slab finite elements. The two constant point loads applied during the tests via
 487 the hydraulic jack and a steel-framed loading tree are applied to single nodes at the third-point
 488 span locations (in the 3D shell model, these nodes are in the slab layer). Dynamic analysis with

489 zero damping (i.e. negligible due to the low velocity of the structural response) is performed via a
490 Newton-Raphson numerical solver to achieve convergence with a criterion of 0.0005 [52]. A
491 comeback routine is used to allow the simulation to continually halve the time step (to a limit of
492 0.0001 seconds) until convergence is reached (i.e. utilizing an adaptive time step to cope with
493 highly nonlinear response).

494

495 *5.1 3D Shell Model*

496 **Fig. 10** shows the full assembly of the 3D shell model, in which the flanges and web of the
497 steel beam were modeled with 4-noded shell elements discretized to a 38.1-mm (1.5-in.) maximum
498 edge dimension. The slab shell elements were modeled with a 282-mm (11.1-in.) maximum edge
499 dimension and constant thickness of 82.55-mm (3.25-in.) corresponding to the minimum structural
500 thickness. The degrees of discretization were obtained via preliminary analyses for mesh
501 convergence and are consistent with the previous efforts of Quiel and Garlock on modeling the
502 fire-exposed performance of thin steel plates [58] and concrete floor slabs in steel-framed buildings
503 [33]. Node layers for all shell elements are located at their structural thickness centerlines per the
504 specimen geometry. All shell elements have 4 integration points in plan and 6 integration points
505 through their depth with Gaussian spacing.

506 The WWR in the slab is represented as an uncoupled smeared layer with equivalent area
507 per width in both the longitudinal and transverse directions. The equivalent reinforcement area in
508 the longitudinal direction matched the WWR in the tested specimens, while that in the transverse
509 direction was increased slightly to account for the flexural contributions of the perpendicular ribs
510 (which were not explicitly modeled). The transverse channel at each end of the beam is included
511 to provide transverse support to the slab, similar to the tested assembly. The channel element was

512 wrapped in several layers of ceramic blankets during the test and did not experience a severe
513 enough temperature increase to cause significant stiffness loss. This element is therefore modeled
514 at ambient temperature.

515 (a)
516 **Fig. 10.** SAFIR shell element model: (a) isometric view and (b) connection region close-up

517 Imperfections were imposed on the geometry of the beam web and bottom flange as
518 bidirectional sinusoidal patterns to enable the emergence of potential local buckling. The top
519 flange received no imperfections because it was braced against the slab and is therefore unlikely
520 to experience local buckling. Per previous research by Quiel and Garlock [58], the amplitude of
521 the imperfections in the web was taken as $d/500$ (calculated to be 0.5 mm, where d is the height of
522 the web plate). Seven sinusoidal wavelengths were imposed along the longitudinal span of the
523 web, and a single half wavelength was imposed over the web depth. The imperfections in the
524 bottom flange (with a maximum amplitude of 0.312 mm) were imposed to be geometrically
525 congruent with those in the web (i.e. to preserve their perpendicular interface). To enable the
526 emergence of potential lateral instability, the steel beam was also given initial out-of-straightness
527 as a lateral shift equal to span/1000 in accordance with guidelines for inelastic analysis in
528 Appendix 1 of AISC 360-16 [16]. This imperfection geometry was developed by first analyzing

529 the beam with no fire and no loads other than a small moment about the longitudinal axis at the
530 interface of the bottom flange and web at midspan. The deformed geometry from this elastic
531 analysis is then overlaid onto the model for structural-fire analysis.

532 The shear studs spaced at every 304.8-mm (1-ft.) were modeled using a connector beam
533 element composed of a single fiber. The structural properties of the connectors were kept at
534 ambient throughout the analysis and given an artificial modulus of elasticity of 500 GPa to ensure
535 they would have a “very stiff” shear response. The element was assigned an arbitrarily large
536 rectangular area of 0.01 m^2 (16 in^2) such that its large moment of inertia would further enhance
537 the connector’s high stiffness. The length of the fiber is 96.8-mm (3.81-in), which is equal to the
538 distance between mid-thickness of the top flange and mid-thickness of the slab’s structural
539 thickness. Based on the steep increase in composite percentage plotted in **Fig. 7**, the viability of
540 using this simplified shear connector element will be demonstrated via comparison to the
541 experimental results. The connector beam elements bridged between vertically aligned nodes in
542 the slab shell layer and the top flange shell layer in the plane of the web. To improve numerical
543 convergence and overcome the effects of localized stress concentration, the rows of nodes on the
544 top flange that include the connector end were assigned the same vertical displacement. For the
545 same reason, these nodes and the two adjacent rows of nodes in the top flange were also assigned
546 the same rotation about the transverse axis. These constraints reasonably approximate the contact
547 of the slab ribs with the top face of the flange at a shear stud location.

548 The shear tab connection was modeled using three single-fiber truss (i.e. axial) elements
549 with individual stiffnesses that are representative of the bolts and their interaction with the
550 connection plates. As shown in **Fig. 10**, each element connected a node on the web (at the
551 approximate location of the actual bolt hole) to a column node at the same vertical location. The

552 web shells sharing the “bolt hole” nodes were thickened to include the shear tab thickness – this
553 was needed to mitigate numerical instabilities from unrealistically high concentrations of stress at
554 these nodes. Since these connectors are axial-only, a vertical displacement constraint was applied
555 between the nodes at each end of the three connector elements.

556 The connector elements were assigned a stiffness of 33.3 kN/mm (190 kip/in) per recent
557 tests of the ambient stiffness of a shear tab connection with three 19.05-mm (3/4-in.) bolts [59].
558 Other previous research has shown that bolt shear capacity at temperatures below 300°C (572°F)
559 is not substantially affected when compared to ambient capacity, and at 600°C (1112°F) shear
560 capacity drops to 20% of ambient [60]. As shown in Part 1 of this study [19], the connection zone
561 remains below 204°C (400°F) during the entirety of the unprotected test, while that in the protected
562 test exceeds reaches a maximum of ~575°C (1067°F) just prior to runaway flexural failure. The
563 ambient stiffness is used as a simplification in the 3D shell analyses presented in this paper and
564 will be shown as providing an acceptable prediction of the connection’s lateral and rotational
565 restraint of thermal expansion as it pertains to the flexural performance of the composite beam.
566 Damage to the connection plates and bolts using detailed, temperature dependent modeling
567 approaches will be evaluated in future work.

568 The 3D shell model was analyzed using steel temperatures from the experimental tests
569 (**Fig. 2**) and the average temperature gradient in the structural (i.e. minimum) slab thickness from
570 the 2D thermal model of the slab on fluted deck (**Fig. 5**). The same thru-thickness temperature
571 profile was uniformly applied to the entire slab, thus conservatively neglecting the slightly lower
572 temperatures that would realistically occur where the slab is in contact with the beam. As shown
573 in **Fig. 10**, the average flange and web temperatures from the test were applied over the majority
574 of the beam length except for the 355-mm (14-in.) segments on both ends that were covered in

575 ceramic fiber blankets during the test. The time history of average temperatures measured at the
576 connections during each test were input into the full section depth (web and both flanges) at the
577 50.8-mm (2-in.) ends of the beam (i.e. at the shear tab connection). The temperature in the web
578 and flange plates over the remainder of the blanket-covered region was linearly ramped from the
579 connection temperature to their corresponding span temperature.

580

581 5.2 2D Fiber-Beam Model

582 As shown in **Fig. 11**, the composite section for the 2D fiber-beam representation of the
583 composite beam and slab was divided into 38 strip fibers over its depth: six in the slab (to match
584 the thermal model's thru-thickness discretization in **Fig. 4**), one for each flange, and the rest
585 equally spaced over the web depth. The WWR is conservatively neglected for simplicity since the
586 slab ends were unrestrained. Future work will examine the influence of a continuous slab condition
587 beyond the steel beam connection – in those cases, the slab reinforcement will play a more
588 significant role and would need to be included in any computational model. The transverse
589 channels were also neglected in the 2D models since out-of-plane **elements cannot be explicitly**
590 **included**.

591

592

Fig. 11. Discretization of the fiber-beam composite cross-section.

593 The 3-noded fiber-beam elements [52] representing the composite beam were discretized
594 at approximately 304.8-mm (1-ft.) lengths per previous research by Quiel and Garlock [33].
595 Simulations of the protected and unprotected tests were performed using two different constraints
596 between the beam's end node and the column node at the same vertical location: displacement
597 only (i.e. pinned), and all displacement and rotational degrees of freedom (i.e. fixed). These nodes
598 are horizontally offset by half the column section depth. The results of these models would be
599 expected to bound the experimental response, for which the shear tab connections would
600 realistically provide a small amount of rotational restraint. Future work will explore the structural
601 ramifications of using a simplified rotational spring or component-based connection model [61]
602 for modeling the fire-induced response of these assemblies.

603 Analyses with the 2D fiber-beam model were made with two sets of thermal input. The
604 first matched that used for the shell model, utilizing the experimentally measured steel
605 temperatures and slab temperature profiles obtained from the 2D thermal model of the slab on
606 fluted deck. The main span steel temperatures were assigned to the full length of the fiber-beam
607 model – the reduced temperatures at the blanketed beams ends and the connection were neglected
608 for conservative simplification. The second set of thermal input, representing a “blind” calculation
609 conducive to design, implements the lumped mass steel temperatures and the average of the 1D
610 flat slab thermal analyses. For both input sets, the bottom and top flange fibers were directly
611 assigned the corresponding temperature-time histories. The same was done for all web fibers
612 except for those directly adjacent to the flanges. These “transition” fibers were assigned an average
613 of the web and flange temperature to smooth the thru-depth thermal gradient and improve
614 numerical convergence.

615

616 5.3 Results

617 5.3.1 Deflections

618 Plots comparing the experimental and numerical time histories of the beam's vertical
619 midspan deflection and horizontal column pushout are provided in **Fig. 12** and **Fig. 13**,
620 respectively, for the protected and unprotected specimens subjected to the ASTM E119 standard
621 fire. Experimental curves represent the average of North/South and East/West measurements made
622 during the tests [19]. The following notation is used to identify each composite beam model:
623 element type with beam-end condition ("S" for shell elements and realistic end connections; "BP"
624 and "BF" for fiber-beam with pinned and fixed ends), and thermal input ("TT" for test
625 temperatures in the beam and the detailed 2D slab profile; "LM" for the lumped mass steel
626 temperatures with the simplified 1D slab profile).

627 As shown in the experimental results in Part 1 of this study [19], the protected specimen
628 showed little evidence of local or lateral flange instability and appeared to develop a plastic
629 mechanism at flexural failure. The unprotected specimen, however, experienced significant lateral
630 sway of its bottom flange during the last minute of the test as it approached runaway failure. To
631 further investigate the role of instability in the failure of the unprotected specimen, a second
632 version of the S-TT model was analyzed in which the node at the interface of the web and bottom
633 flange at midspan was restrained (i.e. braced) in the lateral direction to prevent sway. The results
634 of this analysis, called S-TT-B ("B" for braced), are also plotted in **Fig. 12b** and **Fig. 13b**.

635 **Fig. 12** and **Fig. 13** show some slight initial discrepancy between the ambient numerical
636 and experimental deflections under the applied loads and self-weight – this is most likely caused
637 by realistic flexibility and load-induced settlement in the test setup that is unaccounted for in the
638 models. This initial discrepancy notwithstanding, the TT models show close agreement with the

639 displacements from both tests, with the more precise shell response bounded by the pinned and
 640 fixed fiber-beam models as expected. As the composite beam heats up, its thermal expansion is
 641 partially restrained by the support column, which as a result is pushed outward (i.e. negative
 642 displacement). The downward midspan deflection of the specimen steadily increases with the
 643 beam temperature until accelerating as the maximum steel temperature approaches 700°C (1292°F)
 644 in **Fig. 2** and the combined cross-section approaches 100% composite in **Fig. 7**. As summarized
 645 in **Table 2**, the TT models demonstrate times to runaway failure that are very close and slightly
 646 conservative relative to the experimental results.

647 The LM models also demonstrate good agreement with experimental displacements until
 648 reaching runaway failure about 10-15% earlier. As shown previously in **Fig. 2**, the LM models
 649 predicted slightly higher steel temperatures, especially for the bottom flange and web, relative to
 650 those recorded during the test. Improvements in the LM approach would produce even better
 651 agreement in the time needed to reach flexural failure; however, the current LM predictions are
 652 acceptably conservative to be used as “blind” design-basis calculations.

653
 654 **Fig. 12.** Beam midspan deflection for the (a) protected and (b) unprotected specimens
 655

656
657 **Fig. 13.** Column pushout deflection for the (a) protected and (b) unprotected specimens

658 **Table 2.** Summary of experimental and numerical failure times (in minutes)

		By E119 Deflection Limit (By Runaway)				
Specimen	Exp.	TT Models			LM Models	
		Shell	Beam Pinned	Beam Fixed	Beam Pinned	Beam Fixed
Protected	130 (138)	134 (136)	125 (134)	138 (138)	110 (115)	119 (119)
Unprotected	22 (28)	25 (25)	24 (25)	26 (27)	24 (24)	26 (26)

659

660 The deflected shapes of both the protected (**Fig. 14**) and unprotected (**Fig. 15**) **S-TT models**

661 **(as-tested, unbraced)** at runaway failure are very similar to those observed during testing [19]. The

662 protected beam in **Fig. 14** experiences only minor out-of-plane web deformation near the transition

663 to the cooler blanketed connection zone. As a result, the bottom flange remains relatively straight

664 along the length of the beam. The unprotected beam in **Fig. 15** experiences considerably more

665 local deformation at the same location in its web and bottom flange, leading to considerable lateral

666 sway of the bottom flange as the beam reached runaway. Real-time observations of this specimen

667 during the test via a high-temperature probe camera revealed that the bottom flange sway in the

668 unprotected specimen did not occur until the final few minutes of the test as the beam approached

669 runaway failure. Post-test inspections of both specimens indicated that the bottom flange and the

670 face of the support column did not come into contact due to the relatively low support rotations

671 for the tested span. The relative displacement between the end of the bottom flange and the virtual
672 face of column flange in the 3D shell model of each specimen also indicated no contact between
673 them.

674
675 **Fig. 14.** Final deflected shape of the protected specimen: (a) S-TT model at runaway failure (5x
676 magnified), and (b) post-test inspection photo (with most fire protection removed)
677

678
679
680 **Fig. 15.** Final deflected shape of the unprotected specimen: (a) S-TT model at runaway failure
681 (5x magnified), and (b) post-test inspection photo
682

683 **When the bottom flange of the unprotected model is braced, the S-TT-B results in Fig. 12b**
684 **and Fig. 13b show nearly identical deflection behavior and time to failure as the unbraced as-tested**
685 **S-TT configuration. Even though its bottom flange is prevented from laterally swaying at midspan,**
686 **the deformed shape of the unprotected S-TT-B model at its loss of flexural resistance exhibits very**

687 similar localized web-shear instability near the connection zone as that shown in **Fig. 15a** for the
688 unbraced S-TT. This comparison, as well as the good agreement of deflection and time to failure
689 between these models and the unprotected BP-TT and BF-TT cases, suggests that the web-shear
690 instability exhibited in the shell models emerged after the onset of significant plasticity in the
691 heated steel beam cross-section. Previous experimental [62] and numerical [63] studies have
692 examined the role of web-shear buckling as a limit state for shear-critical steel elements such as
693 deep thin-web bridge girders. Further investigation of the role of web-shear instability as a
694 potential flexural limit state for typical composite floor beams under fire is therefore warranted.
695 Note that all subsequent discussion of S-TT models in the remainder of this paper refer to the as-
696 tested, unbraced configuration.

697

698 5.3.2 Internal Forces

699 Internal axial loads and bending moments in the S-TT, BP-TT, and BF-TT models are
700 plotted in **Fig. 16** and **Fig. 17**, respectively. The internal forces at the end of the 3D shell composite
701 beam were calculated using shell stresses at a cross-section approximately 95.25-mm (3.75-in.)
702 from the end of the beam (i.e. two discretizations past the extent of the shear connection) instead
703 of directly at the beam end (where the flange tips were free and the shear tab shells were thickened).
704 The shell stresses through the depth of the beam at this location represented the maximum reactions
705 for that model. Likewise, the internal forces at the midspan of the 3D shell model were calculated
706 using the shell stresses in from both the slab and beam at their last integration point before midspan.
707 Moment calculations were performed assuming initial relative geometry of the shell integration
708 points. For fiber-beam models, the reactions were measured at the last integration point before the
709 end of the beam or midspan.

710 **Fig. 16** shows that the composite section remains in compression for the full duration of
711 **these** three TT analyses. The **BF-TT** models result in slightly less axial force than the **BP-TT** or **S-**
712 **TT** models due to their development of significant negative end moment, as shown in **Fig. 17**. As
713 expected, the **S-TT** model develops a very small amount of negative end moment due to the small
714 rotational resistance offered by the shear connection. The **BP-TT** model shows a very small amount
715 of positive end moment since the measurement is taken at the last integration point (i.e. not at the
716 absolute end of the beam). Midspan moments are similar for the **S-TT** and **BP-TT** models
717 throughout the analysis. The midspan moments in the **BF-TT** model begin to converge toward
718 those of the other two models near failure after it develops a plastic hinge at its end due to negative
719 moment.

720 In **Fig. 16a**, the protected **S-TT** and **BP-TT** models show very similar axial force, with little
721 variation along the length of the composite beam. **Fig. 16b**, however, shows that the unprotected
722 **S-TT** model experiences more compression at the beam end than at midspan, while that in the **BP-**
723 **TT** and **BF-TT** models remains relatively constant along the beam length. This is caused by the
724 increased temperature difference between the unprotected beam (**Fig. 2a**) and slab (**Fig. 5**) and the
725 presence of the WWR in the shell model's slab. The cooler reinforced slab in the unprotected
726 specimen provides greater axial restraint to the beam's thermal expansion, thus increasing the axial
727 compression along length of the beam from the midspan (where the shell model axial force is
728 similar to the **BP-TT** model) to the end (where the shell axial force is more than 25% larger than
729 the **BP-TT** model). The amplified temperature difference between the slab and beam as well as a
730 cooler support column lead to larger overall axial compression in all unprotected models than in
731 the protected models.

732

733 **Fig. 16.** Axial force (tension positive) in the (a) protected and (b) unprotected specimens

734

735 **Fig. 17.** Bending moment (sagging positive) in the (a) protected and (b) unprotected specimens

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Even though the beam remains in net compression for the duration of the test, **Fig. 18** shows that the bottom flange at midspan remains in tension throughout **these** three TT analyses. The **S-TT** and **BP-TT** models show close agreement, while the **BF-TT** model has less tension due to lower midspan moment. Bottom flange stress at the end of the beam is small in the **S-TT** and **BP-TT** models, while the **BF-TT** model develops larger end compressive forces due to negative moment. **Fig. 18** also marks the time of first plasticity in the bottom flange steel, per temperature-dependent material properties in Eurocode 3 [15]. Once the fixed end reaches plasticity in the **BF-TT** model, its midspan stress trends toward the pinned model behavior. **Combined with the previous discussion of the S-TT-B model, these results also suggest** that the large lateral sway that emerged in the bottom flange of the unprotected test specimen (and to a much smaller extent in the protected specimen) just prior to runaway [19] was not caused by lateral-torsional buckling along the beam's full length. Instead, the plate deformations were most likely caused by localized

750 web-shear instability near the connection zone (which was captured in both shell models shown in
 751 **Fig. 14** and **Fig. 15**) in combination with post-plastic loss of stability in the web and bottom flange
 752 at the midspan. Post-analysis instability checks of the fiber-beam results based on stress in the
 753 flange and web plates along their length indicated no onset of local or lateral torsional buckling.

754
 755 **Fig. 18.** Stress in the bottom flange of the (a) protected and (b) unprotected beams

756

757 5.3.3 Section Mechanics

758 The plastic capacity of a steel cross-section can be characterized by an axial load (P) and
 759 bending moment (M) capacity envelope – the P and M along the capacity envelope can be
 760 normalized by the axial yield force (P_y) and plastic moment (M_p) to obtain a non-dimensional
 761 boundary. As the steel floor beam experiences non-uniform heating, its normalized plastic P - M
 762 envelope begins to warp due to the development of a thru-depth thermal gradient [64]. The P - M
 763 state of the steel beam at each time step can then be normalized and plotted against the plastic
 764 envelope to observe the changes in P - M section mechanics.

765 As a demonstration, the normalized P - M interaction curve for the protected BP-TT steel
 766 beam midspan is plotted in **Fig. 19** at several milestone time steps. Each P - M plot is shown side-
 767 by-side with a corresponding diagram of the stress in each fiber over the depth of the beam. Note
 768 that these figures represent the internal forces in the steel beam only, not the total net section axial
 769 load and moment carried by the composite section (which was plotted previously in **Fig. 16** and

770 **Fig. 17**). Positive P corresponds to tension, and positive M represents sagging moment about the
771 steel beam's geometric centroid. The large open blue circle marks the initial normalized P - M state
772 under ambient conditions, while the solid blue dot corresponds to the time milestone of interest.

773 A $t = 0$ (**Fig. 19a** and **b**), the steel beam at ambient experiences a small tensile load due to
774 sagging moment induced by flexural loading. After 69 minutes of fire exposure (**Fig. 19c** and **d**),
775 restraint of the beam's thermal expansion has generated net compression in the steel (although the
776 bottom flange remains in tension as was also shown in **Fig. 18a**). The raw values of total net section
777 M remain nearly constant relative to the initial positive moment (**Fig. 17a**), but the normalized
778 values of M in the steel beam have increased due to a thermal decrease in plastic capacity (which
779 occurs at steel temperatures above 400°C [15] as shown in **Fig. 2a**) and a slight decrease in the
780 slab's flexural contribution as the steel compresses due to restraint of thermal expansion. As the
781 steel increasingly loses stiffness at $t = 87$ minutes (**Fig. 19e** and **f**), normalized M reverses direction
782 and P transitions back to tension as the percentage of composite action begins to increase more
783 rapidly (**Fig. 7**). Due to the thermal gradient and resulting non-uniform yield strength distribution
784 in the steel section, the plastic envelope has now significantly warped, and the plastic neutral axis
785 of the composite section shifts upward towards the slab. This trend continues through $t = 123$
786 minutes (**Fig. 19g** and **h**), when plasticity is first reached in the bottom flange fiber. At this time,
787 the beam's normalized P - M behavior has nearly reached the warped plastic capacity envelope. The
788 steel material in the bottom flange and web has significantly weakened, and the top flange therefore
789 compensates with a larger tensile force to withstand gravity-induced moment in combination with
790 the slab's compression. As the beam's yield strength continues to decrease with increased
791 temperature, the section becomes increasingly plastic and the beam is eventually unable to take
792 more load, leading to the final converged state just before runaway failure (**Fig. 19i** and **j**).

Fig. 19. Normalized P - M diagrams for the **protected** steel beam at midspan for BP-TT analysis

794 **Fig. 20.** Normalized P - M diagrams for the steel beam at runaway failure for both **protected and**
 795 **unprotected** BP- and BF-TT analyses
 796

797 **Fig. 20** shows the final normalized P - M diagrams just before runaway failure at the
 798 midspan and end of both the BP- and BF-TT steel beams (with **Fig. 19i** reproduced as **Fig. 20a**).
 799 Note that all LM models have similar behavior but reach failure slightly sooner as indicated

800 previously in **Table 2**. **Fig. 20b** shows that the unprotected BP-TT steel beam midspan has a
801 similar P - M trajectory as its protected counterpart but fails much earlier due to the faster
802 temperature increase. The unprotected beam develops a smaller thru-depth thermal gradient (**Fig.**
803 **2b**) and therefore has less warping in its plastic P - M capacity envelope.

804 The end of the beam in both pinned cases (**Fig. 20c** and **d**) develops little moment, and the
805 normalized P - M behavior curves do not reach the capacity envelope at any point during the
806 analysis. In the fixed models, the beam ends (**Fig. 20g** and **h**) experience an increase in normalized
807 negative M until reaching the plastic capacity curve and creating a plastic hinge. Once the steel
808 beam develops these end hinges, the midspan of the fixed models experiences similar P - M
809 behavior compared to the pinned midspan plots.

810

811 **6. Structural Fire Resistance**

812 **Fig. 21** compares the vertical midspan deflection versus (a) bottom flange temperature and
813 (b) average beam temperature from all models against the corresponding test data [19]. Regardless
814 of passive protection or the calculation technique, the plotted relationships between beam
815 temperature and midspan deflection all show good agreement. The LM temperatures are
816 conservative compared to the test temperatures, and the time to runaway failure for structural
817 models with LM input is correspondingly conservative. The structural failure temperatures at the
818 chosen applied load level (which utilizes 35% of the composite beam's ϕM_n [19]) are shown to be
819 100-150°C conservative relative to the ASTM E119 thermal limits (also plotted as vertical lines in
820 **Fig. 21**).

821
 822 **Fig. 21.** Comparisons of deflections versus (a) bottom flange and (b) beam average temperature
 823 for the as-tested loading condition (utilizing 35% ϕM_n)
 824

825 A tabular comparison of ASTM E119 thermal failure criteria against structural
 826 performance is provided in **Table 3**. Beam element model results are averaged between the pinned
 827 and fixed cases. The results show that the models can provide conservatively accurate predictions
 828 of the tested performance. All models at the 35% ϕM_n utilization load (which is about 60% of a
 829 maximum service condition) achieve significant increases in structural fire resistance versus the
 830 E119 thermal limit criteria. All of the models were then reanalyzed with the point loads increased
 831 to utilize 65% ϕM_n to represent a maximum service load condition [19] – the resulting times to
 832 structural failure are also summarized in **Table 3**. All models at the maximum service load show
 833 much closer agreement between deflection-based and thermal limits per ASTM E119. Note that
 834 the shell models were increasingly sensitive to the losses of flexural resistance at this higher load
 835 level – both just reached the E119 deflection limit criteria and then experienced numerical failure
 836 before full runaway could be reached. All beam element models reached full runaway with no
 837 losses of local or global stability detected in post-analysis calculation checks. Similar to **Fig. 21**,
 838 the midspan deflection for the maximum service load models are plotted as a function of (a) bottom
 839 flange temperature and (b) beam average temperature in **Fig. 22**. At the higher load level, the E119
 840 thermal limits show good correlation to the critical temperature of all analyses.

841

842

Table 3. Time needed to reach thermal and deflection limit criteria (in minutes)

Specimen	By E119 Thermal Limit		By E119 Deflection Limit (By Runaway)						
	Exp.	LM	35% ϕM_n				65% ϕM_n		
			Exp.	S-TT	B-TT (avg)	B-LM (avg)	S-TT	B-TT (avg)	B-LM (avg)
Protected	88	75	130 (138)	134 (136)	132 (136)	114 (117)	86 (86)	98 (100)	84 (85)
Unprotected	12	12	22 (28)	25 (25)	25 (26)	25 (25)	14 (14)	15 (15)	15 (15)

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Fig. 22. Comparisons of deflections versus (a) bottom flange and (b) beam average temperature at maximum service load (utilizing 65% ϕM_n)

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To obtain a 2-hr deflection-based rating at the maximum service load, the SFRM thickness was iteratively increased until a 2-hr thermal rating was reached via the aforementioned lumped mass calculations. A resulting thickness of 38.1 mm (1.5 in) reached the maximum temperature limit at $t = 123$ minutes, with the average temperature limit being reached less than two minutes later. The LM thermal results were then used as input for fiber-beam structural models (Fig. 9 and Fig. 11) at the maximum service load (utilizing 65% ϕM_n). Fig. 23 compares the results of these LM fiber-beam calculations with those using the as-tested SFRM thickness of 22.2 mm (7/8 in). Fig. 23a plots the time histories of maximum beam temperature and midspan deflection, and Fig. 23b plots the midspan deflection as a function of maximum beam temperature. All models rapidly

857 approach runaway as the beam temperature reaches the E119 thermal limit, with the fixed analyses
858 lasting 10-20 minutes longer than the pinned analyses.

859
860 **Fig. 23.** Comparisons of SFRM thickness at maximum service load (utilizing 65% ϕM_n): (a) time
861 histories of maximum beam temperature and midspan deflection, and (b) midspan deflection
862 versus maximum beam temperature
863

864 7. Summary and Conclusions

865 Numerical models with varying complexity were validated against the results of structural
866 fire tests on two partially composite, partially restrained large-scale composite floor beams
867 subjected to flexural loading and the ASTM E119 fire curve. The specimens, which were tested in
868 Part 1 of this study [19], are structurally identical and representative of North American composite
869 floor construction. One specimen was coated with spray-applied fire resistive material (SFRM)
870 corresponding to a 2-hr fire resistance rating per UL Design D902 [38] – the other specimen was
871 left unprotected (i.e. as bare steel). Experimental temperatures in the beam conservatively agreed
872 with predictions via a multiple lumped mass (LM) approach with thermally dependent material
873 properties (which are non-iteratively updated using the results at the previous time step). The slab
874 temperatures were predicted using a 2D finite element approach as well as two simplified 1D
875 representations. Structural models composed of either shell elements or fiber-beam elements with
876 varying representations of the shear tab connection were then analyzed using both the calculated

877 thermal input and the experimental temperatures. All models demonstrated conservative
878 agreement with deflections and times to failure obtained from the tests.

879 Based on the results of this study, the following conclusions can be made:

880 1. The three LM heat transfer calculations demonstrated conservative accuracy to predict the
881 increase in steel beam temperature for both the protected and unprotected specimens. The LM
882 approach is non-iterative and could be implemented in either a simple computer code (as was
883 done in this study) or a spreadsheet.

884 2. The 1D heat flow models provided adequate predictions of the thermal gradient through the
885 structural thickness of the slab for use in structural modeling. In this study, a finite element
886 software was used to make these calculations; however, the 1D approach could also be
887 implemented in a simpler computer code or spreadsheet by reducing the slab into lumped mass
888 strips and using the non-iterative one-step lab updating approach that was used for the steel
889 beam calculations. Calculations for the steel and slab temperatures would then require
890 consistent computational effort. More research regarding appropriate strip discretization and
891 time step length would be needed to implement such a non-iterative slab gradient calculation.

892 3. The degree of composite action in these composite beams increased over the duration of each
893 fire test as the steel beam experienced a larger increase in average temperature than the slab or
894 the shear studs. Both assemblies approached 100% composite action just a few minutes prior
895 to the onset of flexural runaway failure.

896 4. 3D shell element models and 2D fiber-beam structural models both conservatively predicted
897 experimental structural failure. In particular, the fiber-beam analyses using the lumped mass
898 thermal results as input provided a simpler “blind” calculation of the composite beam’s
899 structural fire performance, with no calibration or input taken from the test results.

- 900 5. The validated performance-based calculation approaches were used to examine the impact of
901 changes to applied gravity loading and SFRM thickness on the structural fire resistance of the
902 composite floor specimens. These examples demonstrate the utility of these calculations to
903 translate a prescriptive fire resistance rating to structural performance.
- 904 6. Modeling results suggest that the ASTM E119 thermal limit criteria can provide a good
905 prediction of the time to structural failure when the composite beam is loaded to a maximum
906 service condition. With further verification of this correlation for additional assemblies beyond
907 those tested here, designers could potentially use the proposed LM approach to calculate the
908 required SFRM thickness to meet the thermal limit requirements in response to the standard
909 fire. However, such an approach requires more available data of temperature-dependent
910 thermal properties for passive fire protection materials.

911 The models presented here have the potential for parametric evaluation of longer spans,
912 varied beam-slab combinations, varying boundary conditions, varied loading scenarios, and
913 different fire scenarios (such as natural fires with a decay phase or sprinkler suppression). The goal
914 of this effort is to develop a methodology that structural designers can use to structurally interpret
915 the results of ASTM E119 standard fire tests on restrained composite floor assemblies toward the
916 assessment and design of realistic composite floor configurations under fire.

917

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927

928 **9. References**

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